

CULTURAL LEVEL – AN EXPRESSION OF CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT**Choriyev Sanjarbek Anvarovich**Professor, Doctor of Philosophy
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Annotation. This article analyzes cultural level as an important indicator reflecting the degree of cultural development of both society and the individual. Cultural level is defined by a person's ability to acquire and follow knowledge, values, traditions, art, and social norms. The study also highlights that the formation of cultural level is closely connected with education, upbringing, social environment, and mass media. It is argued that a culturally developed society can achieve stable development only when it has citizens with a high cultural level. Furthermore, it is emphasized that the improvement of cultural level strengthens tolerance, aesthetic taste, moral maturity, and social responsibility in society.

Keywords: cultural level, cultural development, spirituality, values, social norms, education and upbringing, aesthetic taste, social progress, cultural environment, personal development.

INTRODUCTION. Cultural level is one of the key indicators reflecting the degree of cultural development of both an individual and society. It expresses how deeply a person has mastered national and universal values, knowledge, traditions, and social norms, as well as their ability to apply them in practical life. In modern society, cultural development is closely connected with education, social environment, professional growth, and information exchange. Therefore, studying cultural level as an expression of cultural development is important for understanding the moral, intellectual, and social maturity of individuals. This article explores the concept of cultural level and its role as a fundamental measure of cultural development.

METHODS. The research is based on a theoretical and analytical approach. The study involves the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical, and sociological literature related to cultural development and cultural level. Comparative analysis is used to identify the relationship between individual cultural behavior and social development processes. In addition, descriptive methods are applied to explain key criteria such as intellectual activity, social knowledge acquisition, professional development, legal maturity, national pride, etiquette, lifestyle culture, consumption behavior, and patriotism. The synthesis method is used to integrate these criteria into a unified understanding of cultural level as a multidimensional phenomenon.

RESULTS. The most important criteria of a person's cultural level related to consciousness are as follows:

a) Intellectual activity. A person's cultural level can be assessed according to their intellectual activity. This is because only a person who begins to feel the need for new information and knowledge in their daily practical activities, who earnestly strives for this knowledge, who acquires new knowledge in order to improve their practical work, who forms a system of new skills based on this knowledge, and who creates new ideas on the basis of acquired knowledge, can be called intellectually active. Intellectual activity also reflects a person's level of thirst for science and knowledge.

At first glance, intellectual activity may seem to be a criterion only for a culturally advanced person. In fact, this is not the case. Intellectual activity has different stages. In particular, its lower stage is manifested as an interest in acquiring information and knowledge necessary for everyday practical activities. The middle stage appears as a systematic effort to acquire new knowledge. At the higher stage of intellectual activity, “creativity, the production of new knowledge and new ideas—in other words, spiritual production—plays the main role.” A person’s cultural level corresponds to the stage of their intellectual activity.

b) A person’s desire to acquire social knowledge. Cultural level is also closely related to a person’s set of views and knowledge about social reality. It is true that the practical effectiveness of social knowledge cannot be compared with that of natural-scientific knowledge. However, this does not mean that social knowledge is of little importance. Such knowledge allows us to describe social reality and understand the events and processes taking place in society. “At the same time, just as physical and chemical knowledge creates new materials and new objects, social knowledge also, in a certain sense, creates a new social reality.”¹ The desire to acquire them reflects a person’s interest in social processes and their awareness of them. Depending on the intensity of this desire, it is possible to assess the level of a person’s cultural development. The effort to understand the essence of social processes indicates a high cultural level, while the opposite reflects deficiencies in a person’s cultural development.

v) Desire to improve professional knowledge and information. A person’s cultural level is assessed based on how thoroughly they have mastered the body of knowledge related to their profession. Professional knowledge and information include theoretical knowledge, data, ideas, facts, and arguments that enable a person to perform their job duties effectively and achieve certain results in their professional activity. Until the middle of the last century, the knowledge acquired by a person while mastering a profession served as a lifelong reserve. However, the acceleration of social development, the increasing volume of information, and the deepening specialization of professions have created the necessity for continuous updating of professional knowledge.

Today, a person who stops following developments in their field for even a year begins to lose professional competence. Therefore, every individual who values their profession and strives to maintain professional mastery pays special attention to mastering all innovations related to their specialty. As a person’s desire for professional knowledge and information increases, their cultural level also rises; conversely, the weakening of this desire inevitably leads to a decline in their cultural level.

g) Legal maturity. A person’s cultural level is determined by the degree of their legal maturity. In order for any individual to be considered legally mature, they must first have acquired a certain level of legal knowledge, understand their legal status in society, and be able to evaluate human rights in relation to moral norms. Among these features, a person’s legal status is particularly important. As is known, in any society a person’s legal status—that is, their position in society—is defined through various laws. This status is determined by legal opportunities created for expressing abilities and talents, satisfying material and spiritual needs, and participating in social life. A person’s cultural level is evaluated based on how well they understand their legal status and how they use it.

¹ Плебанек О.В. Социальное знание: пределы роста // Научно-технические ведомости Санкт-Петербургского государственного политехнического университета. Гуманитарные и общественные науки, 2014, №1.-275-284-с.

A person's legal maturity is connected with their knowledge of rights and responsibilities. Rights are linked to opportunities, while responsibilities are linked to social requirements. Every right reflects the degree of a person's freedom in society and the potential to use this freedom. Responsibilities, on the other hand, represent the expected behaviors and outcomes from an individual within a given society. A culturally developed person, just as deeply as they know their rights, also clearly understands their responsibilities.

d) National pride.“National pride is a concept that is formed on the basis of an individual's or a social group's national self-awareness and expresses a feeling of pride in the material and spiritual heritage left by ancestors, the contribution of one's own nation to world civilization, and the dignity, prestige, and respect of one's people among other nations.”² National pride is a specific aspect of national consciousness and is a concept that is opposed to nationalism. Nationalism claims the superiority of one nation over others and exaggerates various feelings specific to a particular nation. It gives rise to ideas about the “chosen nature” of a nation, as a result of which various historical facts and unique features of its culture begin to be used to belittle other nations. National pride, however, is free from such negative traits.

DISCUSSION.National pride arises on the basis of solid knowledge about a nation's history, religion, and culture. While national pride is an external expression of cultural level, a person's knowledge of national history and culture represents its internal essence. By observing expression, it is possible to determine the underlying essence. A person with a broad scope of such knowledge can be regarded as a cultured individual. Conversely, if the opposite is true, meaning a person's knowledge about the historical development of their homeland and its cultural existence is limited, then their cultural level is low.

The criteria related to behavior and activity that allow us to determine a person's level of cultural development also exist:

a) Domestic culture.In any society, a person's cultural level can be determined by their everyday lifestyle and the system of values in their domestic life. A person's domestic culture consists of skills, habits, and competencies related to their way of living, maintaining and improving their home conditions, working, preserving health, resting, and organizing their free time. In individuals with a low cultural level, these skills and competencies are weak, which negatively affects the quality of life. Such people face difficulties in creating comfortable living conditions and often neglect their health. Weak domestic culture also has a negative impact on the meaningful use of free time. As a person's cultural level increases, they gradually develop the ability to organize life more effectively, improve living conditions, engage in productive work, maintain health, and choose appropriate ways of meaningful rest and leisure.

b) Clothing culture.A person's way of dressing is a clear expression of their cultural development. Clothing is an important indicator that shows to what extent an individual has mastered national and universal cultural values, norms, and traditions related to dressing. In addition, clothing is a means of expressing a person's individuality, character traits, image, and social status. “A person's attitude toward their clothing is a cultural-historical phenomenon.”³ In other words, it is shaped under the influence of various socio-cultural factors. As society develops in socio-cultural terms, a person's clothing culture also continues to improve. However, for this to happen, an individual must not stop accelerating and enriching their own cultural development.

² Nazarov Q. Jahon falsafasi qomusi. Birinchi jild.- T.: O'zb. fayl. milliy jam. nashr., 2019.- B.800.

³ O'sha yerda.

The stronger the intensity of such aspiration, the more developed a person's clothing culture becomes.

v) Eating culture. In human life, the importance of choosing the optimal way, form, and composition of food consumption is incomparable. Food is not merely an object of consumption, but a "carrier of spirituality and culture."⁴ Consequently, it also has axiological value. For this very reason, eating culture, as well as habits and skills related to consumption, play a special role in assessing a person's cultural level. An individual with a low cultural level is unable to choose appropriate ways of consumption, and as a result faces various problems related to their activity and health. For example, scientific research in the field of medicine shows that 70% of diseases are caused by non-compliance with dietary rules.⁵ As a person's cultural level increases, their eating culture also becomes more optimal.

g) The ability to observe etiquette and discipline. A person's cultural level can be determined by the degree to which they have developed the skills of following etiquette and discipline. Etiquette is a set of norms of behavior, rules of conduct in society, and principles that regulate interpersonal relations. Etiquette is characterized by its diversity. For example, there are general etiquette rules that apply to all members of society, as well as specific types of etiquette used only by certain groups in their activities (such as diplomatic etiquette, military etiquette, scientific etiquette, etc.). The level and order of a person's adherence to etiquette are reflected in their discipline. Only a person who is aware of and accepts general and special norms, rules, and principles of behavior can strictly follow etiquette and discipline. It is unreasonable to expect a high cultural level from a person who is unaware of etiquette, does not follow it, and does not adhere to rules of discipline.

d) The ability to use material and spiritual wealth. Material wealth refers to objects that have certain value, such as land, buildings, household items, tools of labor, and so on. Spiritual wealth, on the other hand, consists of values that determine a person's spiritual character, behavior, and way of life. Regardless of the level of concentration of material and spiritual wealth in society, individuals differ in their awareness and use of them. A person with a high cultural level is able to use these resources wisely in their activities. A person whose cultural development has certain deficiencies may not only fail to use them rationally but, in some cases, may not even be aware of them. Therefore, a person's cultural level can be determined by their ability to use material and spiritual wealth.

e) Patriotism. A person's cultural level can also be determined by their degree of patriotism. True patriotism is honest work for the bright future of the homeland and for the prosperity of the country, people, and nation."⁶ "Cultural level is expressed in a person's respect and reverence for the village or city where they were born and raised, where their umbilical cord was buried; in their honoring of their parents, siblings, relatives, and ancestors; and in their pride in the past, present, and future of their homeland."⁷ Serving the interests of the homeland and aligning one's life activities with its interests is an important criterion of a person's cultural level. This is because only a person who has deeply mastered national values, understood the interests of the country, and is aware of the national idea can serve the interests of the homeland. For this very reason,

⁴ Беллон М.А. Культура питания: особенности ценностных смыслов.// Вестник СПбГИК, 2018, №2.- 60-с.

⁵ Qarang: Xoliqova M. Oilada sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishda ovqatlanish madaniyatining o'rni.// www.fencing.uz.

⁶ Choriyev A. Inson falsafasi. Mustaqil shaxs. Ikkinchi kitob.- T.: Chinor ENK, 2002.- B.230.

⁷ O'sha yerda.- B.229-230.

historical figures, great thinkers, statesmen and political leaders, scholars, and intellectuals who have honored national values and deeply understood their meaning and essence have devoted their entire lives to working selflessly for the interests and future of their homeland, and have continuously encouraged their compatriots to do the same. Patriotism reflects a person's cultural maturity, while the absence of such a feeling demonstrates cultural shortcomings.

CONCLUSION. A conceptual and structural interpretation of a person's cultural level helps to express its essence and content from a scientific point of view. These conclusions serve as a theoretical and methodological basis for studying the specific features of today's cultural level of the individual. Thus, cultural level is a concept that expresses the degree of a person's awareness of national and universal values, the extent to which they have mastered the knowledge and ideas accumulated by humanity over centuries, and their ability to act based on these values and knowledge. The level of its formation is determined through a number of criteria related to human consciousness and activity. A person's cultural level changes under the influence of various objective conditions and subjective factors.

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